

Natural and constructed wetlands to remove pollutants and potentiate water reuse

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Abstract

Wetlands include a wide variety of ecosystems, no deeper than six meters at low tide, as well as human-made wetlands (Ramsar Convention Secretariat, 2010).

Natural wetlands, including saltmarshes located in estuarine areas, have long been used as uncontrolled discharge sites for different sources of wastewaters due to their recognition for water quality improvement. In natural wetlands, wastewater flows over the large wetland surface and mixes with the wetland water. The high organic load of the wetland soils contributes to the physical, chemical and biological removal processes, whereas, simultaneously, the wetland vegetation up takes nitrogen and phosphorus and other compounds. Saltmarsh plants and their associated microbial communities have an important role in the removal of contaminants from estuaries. Plant roots and rhizomes can act as a net and/or promote the retention of thin sediments leading to a decrease in water flow and turbulence in these areas, which consequently leads to the retention/accumulation of pollutants. Estuarine saltmarshes can therefore, act as sink of pollutants released by different anthropogenic activities, including agricultural, industrial and domestic discharges, since many urban areas are located close to estuarine areas. Moreover, not only urban areas, but also aquaculture and ports are main factors contributing to anthropogenic pressure in estuaries. Among contaminants we can find metals, endocrine disrupting chemicals, pesticides and petroleum hydrocarbons, and contaminants of emergent concern (CECs) like pharmaceuticals and saltmarsh plants, along with their rhizosphere microbial communities, have proven to be phytoremediation agents in the retention and/or removal of several of these contaminants. Using the Lima river estuary as a case study, this presentation will show the potential of saltmarsh to remove different contaminants (e.g. metals, microplastics, pharmaceuticals and other CECs) from the aquatic environment, preventing them from spreading in the area and from reaching coastal areas and/or eventually contaminating underlying aquifers.

Constructed wetlands (CWs), or treatment wetlands, are low-cost engineered systems designed to mimic natural wetland processes, using wetland vegetation, soils/substrate and associated microorganisms to treat wastewater. Pollutants removal is reached through a combination of physical, chemical and biological processes in which all the elements of CWs, plants, microorganisms and substrates, can have a significant influence. Reusing treated wastewater represents an important part of sustainable water resource management and circular economy, reducing the use of freshwater. However, wastewaters need to be adequately treated before its reuse to remove a wide variety of pollutants such as pesticides, pharmaceuticals or metals and CWs can be an option. Current presentation will show the potential of CWs for pollutants removal, including metals and CECs, and its potential application for water reuse.

Keywords: *estuarine saltmarshes, treatment wetlands, pharmaceuticals, metals, good water quality*

Biography

Marisa Almeida (MA) is a senior researcher (PhD in Chemistry in 2003) at CIIMAR since 2005 with ca. 150 international peer review publications. Her main research area is bio- and phytoremediation, being actively involved in advancing the application of these techniques in biotechnology for the remediation of aquatic environments contaminated with different pollutants. She serves as the Principal Investigator of the Environmental Chemistry and Recovery team at CIIMAR. Her expertise spans environmental chemistry applied to coastal and estuarine environments, and phytoremediation of contaminants in natural and constructed wetlands, currently coordinating four European projects. MA has been (co)supervising PhD, MSc and graduation students, being also actively engaged in science outreach initiatives. MA is also involved in teaching at the Faculty of Science, University of Porto. She also contributes to COST actions, evaluates project proposals and theses, and serves as invited reviewer and is part of the editorial board of scientific journals.

Acknowledgments: To project Mar2Protect (GA N° 101082048) funded by European Union Horizon Europe,